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FINAL ANALYSIS:

COVI-PREG – CONSIGN WP2

Follow up of infants

COVID-19 and medicines in pregnancy for the CONSIGN consortium

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PASS Information

Title	Neurodevelopment follow up of infants born from mother tested positive to SARS-CoV-2 during pregnancy
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Countries of study	Switzerland United States of America Brazil Saudi Arabia
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Table of contents

1. ABSTRACT	5
2. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	6
3. INVESTIGATORS	7
4. OTHER RESPONSIBLE PARTIES	7
5. MILESTONES	8
6. RATIONALE AND BACKGROUND	8
7. OBJECTIVE	9
8. AMENDMENTS AND UPDATES	10
9. RESEARCH METHOD	10
Study design.....	10
Setting	10
Subjects	10
Exposure to SARS-CoV-2 infection.....	11
Study procedures	11
Ethical approvals	11
Outcome - Infant Neurodevelopment	11
Covariates	13
Demographics' characteristics.....	13
Obstetrical and medical history.....	13
Maternal co-variates – definitions	13
Pregnancy co-variates – definitions.....	13
Maternal COVID-19 related medicine use - definition	14
Neonatal co-variates - definitions	14
Statistical analysis	14
10. RESULTS	14
Participants.....	14
Descriptive data	14
Outcome data and main results	17
Ongoing data collection.....	21
11. DISCUSSION	21
Key results	21

Limitations	23
Interpretation	23
12. CONCLUSION	24
13. DISCLAIMER.....	24
14. REFERENCES	25

1. ABSTRACT

Title

Neurodevelopment follow up of infants born from mother tested positive to SARS-CoV-2 during pregnancy

Keywords

SARS-CoV-2; infants follow-up; in utero SARS-CoV-2 exposure; neurodevelopment; COVID-19

Rationale and Background:

Pregnant women tested positive for SARS-CoV-2 reported an increased risk of maternal, pregnancy and neonatal adverse outcome. Since the beginning of the pandemic, numerous pregnant women were exposed to SARS-CoV-2. This is not without consequences as maternal immune activation impact the fetal immune response and influence the development of the fetal brain. There is an urgent need to evaluate the association between SARS-CoV-2 in utero exposure and the development of children.

Research question and objective

The aim was to describe the neurodevelopment of infants exposed to SARS-CoV-2 in-utero using the ASQ-3 questionnaire until 24 months of life.

Study design

Pregnant women were initially enrolled prospectively during pregnancy using the multi-centric international COVI-PREG registry. Patients who delivered a live born infant were sent a neurodevelopment questionnaire at 6/8 12/14 and 24/27 months that they self-answered. Every data were collected through an online secure database

Setting

Pregnant patients recruited in the COVI-PREG registry were called at 6/8, 12/24, and 24/27 months after birth and asked if they want to participate to this follow up study. Recruitment occurred from September 2021 to May 2022.

Subjects

Pregnant women tested positive for SARS-CoV-2 during their pregnancy and delivered a live born infant at 24 weeks of gestation (wk) or more were eligible for inclusion. Patients with a condition known to be a major bias for neurodevelopmental anomaly were excluded (e.g., Down syndrome, congenital cytomegalovirus infection with brain lesions at ultrasound scanning).

Variables and data sources

The outcome of interest was the ASQ-3 scores in the 5 filled assessed by the questionnaire. Co-variables included demographics' characteristics, obstetrical history, medical history, course of maternal COVID-19, course of pregnancy, maternal COVID-19 medicine use and neonatal characteristics at birth.

Results

The study included 30 pregnant patients and their infants in the study. The number of infants assessed at 6, 8, 12, 14 and 24 months were 1, 15, 2, 9, and 3 respectively. Regardless of the period of assessment, neurodevelopment was categorized as low in 10 infants including 6 (20%; 95%CI [8-39]) patients in gross motor, 1 (3%; 95%CI [0-17]) in fine motor and 5 (17%; 95%CI [6-35]) in personal social. Out of 10, 2 were born extremely preterm and 8 at term (37 to 41 weeks of gestation).

Conclusion

We did not report any signals of substantial neurodevelopmental delay in the children born from mothers tested positive to SARS-CoV-2 during pregnancy. No firm conclusions can be drawn at present regarding more moderate levels of delay as the number of cases included was too small.

Names and affiliations of principles investigators

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2. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Anti-IL 6: anti-interleukin 6

ASQ-3: ages and stages questionnaire version 3

BMI: body mass index

COVI-PREG: coronavirus and pregnancy registry

HCCQ: hydroxychloroquine

HIV: human immunodeficiency virus

ICU: intensive care unit

IQR: interquartile range

IUGR: intrauterine growth restriction

NICU: neonatal intensive care unit admission

REDCap: research electronic data capture secure web application

RT-PCR: retro transcriptase polymerase chain reaction

SAP: statistical analysis plan

SD: standard deviation

TOP: termination of pregnancy

wk: weeks of gestation

3. INVESTIGATORS

Name	Institution	Role	Contribution
Alice PANCHAUD	University of Bern	COVI-PREG PI, pharmaco-epidemiologist	Primary author
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5. MILESTONES

Milestone	Planned date	Actual date	Comments
Start of data collection	September 2021	01.09.2021	-
End of data collection	Undetermined	Ongoing data collection	-
Registration in the EU PAS register	March 2021	29.03.2021	-
Final report of study results	31.10.2022	31.10.2022	-

6. RATIONALE AND BACKGROUND

As of June 2022, the COVID-19 pandemic resulted in more than 500 million positive tests for the virus and this is still increasing.¹ Pregnant women were not spared and it has been reported that they are at greater susceptibility of infection compared to the same age population.² It is clearly known now that pregnant women are at increased risk of severe disease with a higher risk of intensive care unit (ICU) admission, mechanical ventilation and death due to SARS-CoV-2 compared to the non-pregnant of the same age^{3,4}. Pregnant women tested positive have also increased risk of pregnancy adverse outcomes, including a higher rate of preterm-birth.⁵ Vertical transmission COVID-19 remains rare but can lead to potentially dramatic neonatal outcomes with extensive brain damages.^{6,7}

The published incidence rates for SARS-CoV-2 infection have been reported between 5.4 and 9% throughout the pregnancy and this was before the emergence of Omicron variant which spread massively compared to the previous ones.⁸⁻¹⁰ Although vertical transmission remains rare, numerous pregnant women were exposed to SARS-CoV-2. This is not without consequences as maternal immune activation due to infection impact the fetal immune response and could play a role in the development of the fetal brain.¹¹⁻¹³

In utero exposure to other viruses, such as Zika virus, was associated with altered long term development in children diagnosed with congenital Zika syndrome but also in children tested negative at birth.^{14,15} Similarly, HIV has been associated with long term altered neurological children development whether infants were infected at birth, or not infected but exposed in utero to maternal HIV.^{16,17}

Additionally, pregnant women tested positive for SARS-CoV-2 are at increased risk of preterm birth.^{5,18} This indirect impact of the virus is also of major concern as preterm new-borns are at risk of neurodevelopment delay compared to full-term infants and thus require specific management and interventions in the first years of life.¹⁹

Finally, COVID-19 treatment has been extremely challenging in adults and especially in pregnant women as they were mostly excluded from clinical trials. Repurposing medicines have been proposed even with scarce or inexistent safety or benefit evidence (EMA/CONSIGN WP2 – COVIPREG final report - 06.09.2022)

There is an urgent need to evaluate the association between SARS-CoV-2 in utero exposure and the development of children as early identification of neurodevelopment disorder allow early intervention and long-term benefit.²⁰

7. OBJECTIVE

The aim of the study was to describe the neurodevelopment of infants exposed to SARS-CoV-2 in-utero using the ASQ-3 questionnaire at 6, 8,12,14, 24 and 27 months, born from patients included in the COVI-PREG prospective cohort study.

8. AMENDMENTS AND UPDATES

None

9. RESEARCH METHOD

The method has been described in the statistical analysis plan (SAP) version 3 that detailed the COVI-PREG data collection process for the EMA objectives.

Study design

COVI-PREG is a prospective observational study including pregnant women exposed to SARS-CoV-2, aiming to assess the impact of SARS-CoV-2 in pregnant women. Pregnant women who had a suspected SARS-CoV-2 infection were eligible to the COVI-PREG registry study. They could be either tested because of symptoms, potential virus exposure or universal screening according to local recommendations of the collaborating centre. Only patients with a confirmed positive nasopharyngeal reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) or an antigen test were included in the study. Patients were recruited at the time of the SARS-CoV-2 positive test. The local investigator of the centre who included the patient completed a first form regarding patient's baseline characteristics, COVID-19 onset and testing information, at the time of the inclusion. A first follow-up form was completed either at the end of the COVID-19 events or at the end of the pregnancy, regarding maternal outcomes following the COVID-19 event. A second follow-up form was completed, regarding pregnancy and neonatal outcomes, at the end of the pregnancy, after discharged from maternity unit. Data were collected individually from medical records and stored as de-identified data, recorded in the REDCap (Research Electronic Data Capture) secure online database, designed for the COVI-PREG registry.

Here, we describe the specific method for the analysis of the follow up of infants exposed in utero to SARS-CoV-2.

Setting

Patients were recruited using the COVI-PREG registry. Centres participating in the COVI-PREG register were invited to opt into this follow up of infants study. Initially, eight sites reported interest in this. Meetings were arranged with sites to explore feasibility, required ethical approvals and the study processes. Patients were recruited by their local centres to participate to the neurodevelopmental study from September 2021 to May 2022.

Subjects

Pregnant women tested positive for SARS-CoV-2 during their pregnancy and delivered at 24 weeks of gestation (wk) or more were eligible for inclusion. Patients that had a stillbirth, a late termination of pregnancy, a delivery of a non-viable infant or neonatal death were not

included. Patients who did not speak the available languages (English, French, German, Spanish and Portuguese) of the infant development questionnaires were not eligible. Patients with a condition known to be a major bias for neurodevelopmental anomaly were excluded such as specific antenatal infections, malformation or other condition that is reported to be related to poorer neurodevelopment in infants were excluded (e.g., confirmed cytomegalovirus with brain lesion at ultrasound scan, fetal alcohol syndrome, congenital hypothyroidism, genetic malformations, twin pregnancy complications etc.).

Exposure to SARS-CoV-2 infection

A pregnant woman exposed to SARS-CoV-2 was defined as a patient who came to an antenatal care facility and tested positive for SARS-CoV-2 either with a RT-PCR or an antigen test during the pregnancy during which the foetus was exposed in utero. A positive serology was not sufficient to be considered as exposed because the exposure potentially occurred before pregnancy. SARS-CoV-2 exposure was categorized into trimester 1 (last menstrual period to <14 wk), trimester 2 (14 to 27 wk + 6 days) and trimester 3 (\geq 28 wk).

Study procedures

At the time of the neurodevelopment assessment time point, the included women were phone called by the local investigator, informed and asked if they wished to participate to the neurodevelopmental study. Each participating centre was responsible for calling their respective patients. Patient's participation was voluntary. If patients accepted to participate in the study, information about baseline characteristics and medical data were extracted manually from medical records. The ASQ-3 questionnaire was then sent by post mail to parents with a pre-stamped envelope to return the completed questionnaire to the local investigator. De-identified data were then recorded in the online REDCap secure web application.

Ethical approvals

The study was approved by the Swiss Ethical Board (CER-VD-2020-00548) and the local ethics boards at each participating centre.

Outcome - Infant Neurodevelopment

The neurodevelopment of infant was assessed using the Ages and Stages Questionnaire, third edition (ASQ-3)²¹. This questionnaire is answered directly by the parents at home with their child. It assesses 5 aspects of the neurodevelopment of the infant: communication, gross motor, fine motor, problem solving and personal-social activities. Each field has 6 questions with 3 answers possible: yes, sometimes and not yet, scoring for 10, 5 and 0 respectively. Every field of the development is scored on a total of 60. Questionnaires are different depending on the age of the infant. In this study, infant neurodevelopment was assessed at 3 time points (figure 1):

-5 months to 8 months and 30 days (using either the 6 months or the 8 months questionnaire)

-11 months to 14 months and 30 days (using either the 12 months or the 14 months questionnaire)

-23 months to 28 months and 15 days (using either the 24 months or the 27 months questionnaire)

For infants born preterm, corrected ages were used by subtracting the number of weeks of prematurity (less than 37 weeks) from the child's chronological age, only for the ASQ-3 6, 8, 12 and 14 months, according to the ASQ-3 assessments tool recommendations.²²

Figure 1: Time points for the infant neurodevelopment follow up

Infant development was assessed using a validated cut-off, defined as 2 standard deviation (SD) below the mean, where the infant is potentially delayed in a domain of his/her development and should be evaluated by a professional.²³

If the infant is scored below the cut-off, the development is considered as abnormal. The ASQ-3 also gives an intermediate cut-off defining an intermediate zone (defined as a score $\geq 1SD$ and $< 2SD$) in which the infant is considered as having a normal neurodevelopment but at the limit and should be stimulated and reassess later. Infants are then categorized in low, intermediate and normal neurodevelopment according to these validated cut-offs (table 1).²³

Table 1: ASQ-3 individual cut offs for low, intermediate and normal neurodevelopment.

	6 months		8 months		12 months		14 months		24 months		27 months	
	2.0 SD	1.0 SD	2.0 SD	1.0 SD	2.0 SD	1.0 SD	2.0 SD	1.0 SD	2.0 SD	1.0 SD	2.0 SD	1.0 SD
Communication	29.65	39.27	33.06	42.73	15.62	29.43	17.4	31.63	25.17	38.20	24.02	37.22
Gross motor	22.25	33.95	30.61	41.35	21.49	35.71	25.8	39.44	38.07	46.40	28.01	39.14
Fine motor	25.14	37.04	40.15	47.95	34.5	43.36	23.06	34.97	35.16	43.43	18.42	31.08
Problem solving	27.72	39.06	36.17	45.05	27.32	38.16	22.56	34.82	29.78	39.59	27.62	38.79
Personal social	25.34	36.83	35.84	44.6	21.73	33.73	23.18	35.76	31.54	41.34	25.31	36.11

- *6, 8, 12, 14, 24 and 27 months ASQ-3 questionnaires assess respectively the neurodevelopment of infant between 5 months 0 days and 6 month 30 days, 7 months 0 days and 8 month 30 days, 11 months 0 days and 12 month 30 days, 13 months 0 days and 14 month 30 days, 23 months 0 days and 25 month 15 days and 25 months 16 days and 28 month 15 days.

- SD: standard deviation below mean

- 2.0 SD represents the referral cut-off. A score inferior or equal to the referral cut-off indicates a possible delay in development (further assessment with a professional is recommended)

- 1.0 SD represents the monitoring cut-off. The monitoring zone is defined as a score superior or equal to 1 SD and inferior to 2 SD. Scores

higher than the monitoring zone indicate a typical development. Scores in the monitoring zone may need further investigation

Covariates

Demographics' characteristics

Basic characteristics were collected: maternal age in years, ethnicity, country of residence, education level (University/college or equivalent, intermediate, secondary school, primary school or less or unknown), maternal weight, height and body mass index (BMI) (kg/m²).

Obstetrical and medical history

Obstetrical and medical history was also recorded: multiparous status (defined as at least one previous delivery ≥ 20 wk), previous mode of delivery (caesarean section, vaginal delivery), and previous adverse pregnancy outcomes (including early miscarriages < 14 wk, late miscarriage ≥ 14 wk, termination of pregnancy and stillbirth), and previous pregnancy complications (e.g. pregnancy hypertension, post-partum haemorrhage). Medical history/comorbidity was also collected (e.g. neurological medical history, thyroid imbalance). Maternal addiction was defined as the use of alcohol, tobacco or other drug misuse during the ongoing pregnancy. Number of foetuses and current pregnancy complications before exposure to SARS-CoV-2 were recorded.

Maternal co-variables – definitions

Inpatient management was defined as at least one night spent in a hospital ward for COVID-19 reasons. ICU admission referred to any stay in such a unit. Maternal mechanical ventilation was the requirement of an invasive ventilation. Outpatient was defined as a patient that never spent a night at hospital for COVID-19 but who could have been followed through hospital visits.

Pregnancy co-variables – definitions

Ongoing pregnancy conditions were defined as any condition occurring before SARS-CoV-2 exposure. Ongoing pregnancy complications were defined as any complication occurring after the SARS-CoV-2 infection, including for instance preterm premature rupture of membranes, threatened preterm labour, gestational diabetes etc. Fetal lung maturation was defined as any antenatal steroid for the induction of fetal lung maturation, for any reason. Preterm birth was defined as a birth before 37 wk and was categorized in 3 categories: moderate 32 to 36 wk + 6 days, severe 28 to 31 wk + 6 days and extreme < 28 wk. Mode of delivery was categorized into 5 categories: vaginal delivery after spontaneous labour, vaginal delivery after induction of labour, caesarean section after spontaneous labour, caesarean section after induction, elective caesarean section or emergency caesarean section out of labour. COVID-19 reason for caesarean delivery was defined as a caesarean delivery indication directly related to COVID-19 condition either for maternal or foetal reasons.

Maternal COVID-19 related medicine use - definition

An exposure to a COVID-19 related medicine was defined as the use of a medicine for treating COVID-19 during pregnancy among the following medicine categories: antibiotics, antivirals, hydroxychloroquine, anti-IL6 and immunoglobulin. Substances names were also recorded among each category.

Neonatal co-variates - definitions

New-born sex referred to the sex assigned at birth based on genitalia and/or karyotype and was reported as female, male or undetermined. Neonatal small for gestational age <10th percentile was assessed according to the INTERGROWTH 21st scale. Neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) admission was recorded as well as the reason for NICU admission which could be multiple. New-borns were tested for SARS-CoV-2 PCR or serology (anti-SARS-CoV-2 IgM and IgG) at birth according to local recommendations. Cord blood PCR was defined as a PCR performed on the blood taken from the umbilical cord within the minutes after birth. Neonatal nasopharyngeal PCR was performed during the maternity stay; no precision on the timing of testing was available.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to report patients' baseline characteristics, as well as other co-variates, using absolute numbers (n) and proportions (%). ASQ-3 subdomains' scores were reported as medians with interquartile ranges (IQR) for the overall population and were reported according to the age's periods. Neurodevelopment categories (low, intermediate and normal) were reported in absolute numbers (n) and proportions (%) associated with the 95% confidence intervals (95%CI). Statistical analyses were performed using Stata 16 (StataCorp. 2015. Stata Statistical Software: Release 16. College Station, TX: StataCorp LP).

10. RESULTS

Participants

Out of 8 centres that initially intended to participate to the follow up study, only two were able to start recruitment within the study timeframe: Lausanne, Switzerland and Los Angeles, United States. A total of 68 patients were called, 50 answered and accepted and 30 returned the questionnaire fully completed within the study timeframe.

Descriptive data

Patient's characteristics are presented in table 2 and 3. Median maternal age was 32. The majority were married or in domestic partnership (n=24; 80%) and were of white ethnicity

(n=21; 70%). Three patients (10%) were obese at the inclusion with a BMI of more than 35. Multiparous were represented by 50% (n=15) of patients. Patients with an addiction during pregnancy were 3 (10%) including tobacco use for all and 1 with concomitant cocaine misuse. Exposure to SARS-CoV-2 occurred during trimester 1 in 2 (7%) patients, trimester 2 in 14 (47%) patients and trimester 3 in 11 (37% patients). One (3%) patient was exposed to both clarithromycin and hydroxychloroquine as a COVID-19 related medicine during pregnancy. The same patient (3%) was admitted to intensive care unit requiring oxygen supplementation while all others were managed as outpatients. Neonates were preterm in 4 patients (13%) including 2 (7%) extreme pre-term births (<28 wk). Patients delivered by caesarean section in 37% (n=11). One (3%) patient had a caesarean delivery directly related to COVID-19. Among 30 neonates, 16 (53%) were female and 13 (44%) were male (one was missing). Neonatal weight was under 10th percentile in 2 (7%). A total of 5 (17%) neonates required NICU admission including 4 (13%) for prematurity.

Blood umbilical cord PCR tests were performed in 14 (47%) of new-borns and were all negative. Nasopharyngeal PCR tests was performed in 12 (40%) and one (3%) was positive

Table 2: Patients' baseline characteristics, n=30

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS		
Maternal age (in years) - median; IQR	32	28 - 35
Marital status - n %		
<i>Married or domestic partnership</i>	24	80%
<i>Single never married</i>	2	7%
<i>Unknown</i>	4	13%
Ethnicity - n %		
<i>White</i>	21	70%
<i>Hispanic or Latino</i>	3	10%
<i>Black or African American</i>	1	3%
<i>Asian or Pacific islander</i>	3	10%
<i>Other</i>	2	7%
Region of residence - n %		
<i>Switzerland</i>	27	90%
<i>United States</i>	3	10%
Education level - n %		
<i>University or college or equivalent</i>	5	17%
<i>Intermediate</i>	9	30%
<i>Secondary school</i>	6	20%
<i>Primary school or less</i>	1	3%
<i>Unknown</i>	9	30%
Maternal weight (kg) - median / IQR	71	60 - 79
Maternal height (cm) - median / IQR	165	160 - 167
Maternal BMI (kg/m ²) - median / IQR	25.6	24.0 - 29.0
<i>BMI ≥ 30</i>	4	13%
<i>BMI ≥ 35</i>	3	10%
OBSTETRICAL and MEDICAL HISTORY - n %	n	%
Multiparous	15	50%
<i>Previous caesarean-section</i>	6	20%
<i>Previous vaginal delivery</i>	8	27%
<i>Previous early miscarriage ≥1</i>	7	23%
<i>Previous late miscarriage ≥1</i>	1	3%

<i>Previous TOP</i>	3	10%
<i>Previous stillbirth</i>	1	3%
Previous pregnancy complications		
<i>Any previous pregnancy complication</i>	3	10%
<i>Hypertension in pregnancy</i>	1	3%
<i>Preterm birth</i>	1	3%
<i>Postpartum haemorrhage</i>	1	3%
Medical history		
<i>Any medical history</i>	6	20%
<i>Neurological</i>	3	10%
<i>Thyroid imbalance</i>	2	7%
<i>HIV infection</i>	1	3%
Maternal addiction		
<i>Any addiction</i>	3	10%
<i>Cocaine</i>	1	3%
<i>Tobacco</i>	2	7%
<i>Alcohol</i>	0	0%
ONGOING PREGNANCY - n %	n	%
Singletons	30	100%
Ongoing pregnancy condition (before exposure to the virus)		
<i>Any ongoing adverse pregnancy condition</i>	2	7%
<i>Suspicion of macrosomia</i>	1	3%
<i>Threatened preterm labour</i>	1	3%
FETAL LUNG MATURATION (any reason) - n %	n	%
Antenatal steroids for induction of fetal lung maturation	3	10%

IQR: interquartile range

BMI: body mass index

TOP: termination of pregnancy

HIV: human immunodeficiency virus

Table 3: Patients SARS-CoV-2 exposure, course of COVID-19, pregnancy and neonatal outcomes, n=30

EXPOSURE TO SARS-CoV-2 - n %	n	%
<i>Trimester 1 (<14 wk)</i>	2	7%
<i>Trimester 2 (14 to 27+6 wk)</i>	14	47%
<i>Trimester 3 (≥ 28 wk)</i>	11	37%
<i>Unknown</i>	3	10%
COVID-19 MEDICATION / TREATMENT MANAGEMENT - n %	n	%
ANTIBIOTICS	1	3%
<i>Clarithromycin</i>	1	3%
ANTIVIRALS	0	0%
HCQ	1	3%
CORTICOSTEROIDS	0	0%
ANTI-IL6	0	0%
IMMUNOGLOBULIN	0	0%
COURSE OF MATERNAL SARS-CoV-2 INFECTION - n %	n	%
Outpatient management	29	97%

ICU admission + Mechanical ventilation	1	3%
COURSE OF THE PREGNANCY - n %		
Ongoing pregnancy complication after COVID-19 exposure		
Any ongoing pregnancy complication after exposure	8	27%
PPROM	1	3%
Threatened preterm labour	1	3%
IUGR	2	7%
Gestational diabetes	2	7%
Preeclampsia	1	3%
Placental abruption	2	7%
Preterm birth		
32 - 36+6 wk	2	7%
28 - 31+6 wk	0	0%
<28 wk	2	7%
Mode of delivery		
VAGINAL DELIVERY after spontaneous labour	11	37%
VAGINAL DELIVERY after induction of labour	6	20%
CESAREAN SECTION after spontaneous labour	0	0%
CESAREAN SECTION after induction of labour	2	7%
ELECTIVE CESAREAN SECTION	4	13%
EMERGENCY CESAREAN SECTION OUT OF LABOR	5	17%
Unknown	2	7%
Assisted delivery among vaginal delivery (n=17)	2	12%
C-section related to COVID-19	1	3%
NEONATAL STATUS - n %		
New-born sex		
Female	16	53%
Male	13	43%
Unknown	1	3%
Neonatal weight <p10	2	7%
NICU admission	5	17%
Reason for NICU admission: (multiple reasons possible)		
Prematurity	4	13%
Respiratory distress	2	7%
Hyperbilirubinemia	1	3%
Coagulopathy	1	3%
NEONATAL SARS-CoV-2 TEST AT MATERNITY - n %		
Cord blood PCR performed	14	47%
Cord blood PCR test positive	0	0%
Nasopharyngeal PCR test performed	12	40%
Nasopharyngeal PCR test positive	1	3%

wk: weeks of gestations

HCQ: hydroxychloroquine

ANTI-IL6: anti-interleukin 6

ICU: intensive care unit admission

IUGR: intrauterine growth restriction

NICU: neonatal intensive care unit admission

Outcome data and main results

Among 30 infants, all were assessed at one single time point.

Proportions of infants classified in low, intermediate and normal neurodevelopment are described in table 4 according to the ASQ-3 cut-offs. Regardless of the period of assessment,

neurodevelopment was categorized as normal in 28 (98%; 95%CI [78-99]) for communication, 20 (67%; 95%CI [47-83]) in gross motor, 27 (90%; 95%CI [69-96]) for fine motor, 26 (87%; 95%CI [69-96]) for problem solving, and 20 (67%; 95%CI [47-83]) for personal social. Neurodevelopment was categorized as low in 6 (20%; 95%CI [8-39]) patients in gross motor, 1 (3%; 95%CI [0-17]) in fine motor and 5 (17%; 95%CI [6-35]) in personal social.

Table 4: Proportion of infants classified in low, intermediate and normal neurodevelopment, overall

	Low*			Intermediate*			Normal*		
	n	%	95%CI	n	%	95%CI	n	%	95%CI
TOTAL follow up - n = 30									
Communication	0	-		2	6.7%	0.8 - 22.1	28	93.3%	77.9 - 99.2
Gross motor	6	20.0%	7.7 - 38.6	4	13.3%	3.8 - 30.7	20	66.7%	47.2 - 82.7
Fine motor	1	3.3%	0.1 - 17.2	2	6.7%	0.8 - 22.1	27	90.0%	73.5 - 97.9
Problem solving	0	-		4	13.3%	3.8 - 30.7	26	86.7%	69.3 - 96.2
Personal social	5	16.7%	5.6 - 34.7	5	16.7%	5.6 - 34.7	20	66.7%	47.2 - 82.7

One patient was assessed with the ASQ-3 6 months, 15 with the 8 months, 2 with the 12 months, 9 with the 14 months and 3 with the 24 months questionnaire. ASQ-3 scores' medians as well as proportions of infants classified as low intermediate and normal neurodevelopment, regarding the period of assessment are described in table 5 and illustrated in figure 3.

Table 5: ASQ-3 questionnaires scores' medians with interquartile ranges and neurodevelopment categories, by period of assessment

	ASQ-3 scores			Neurodevelopment categories								
	Median	IQR	ASQ-3 Cut-off	Low n	%	95%CI	Intermediate n	%	95%CI	Normal n	%	95%CI
Follow up at 6 months - n = 1												
Communication	45.0	45.0 - 45.0	29.65	0			0			1	100.0%	25.0 - 100.0
Gross motor	25.0	25.0 - 25.0	22.25	0			1	100.0%	25.0 - 100.0	0		
Fine motor	50.0	50.0 - 50.0	25.14	0			0			1	100.0%	25.0 - 100.0
Problem solving	35.0	35.0 - 35.0	27.72	0			1	100.0%	25.0 - 100.0	0		
Personal social	60.0	60.0 - 60.0	25.34	0			0			1	100.0%	25.0 - 100.0
Follow up at 8 months - n = 15												
Communication	55.0	50.0 - 55.0	33.06	0			0			15	100.0%	78.2 - 100.0
Gross motor	55.0	30.0 - 60.0	30.61	4	26.7%	7.8 - 55.1	1	6.7%	0.0 - 30.8	10	66.7%	69.2 - 100.0
Fine motor	60.0	60.0 - 60.0	40.15	0			0			14	93.3%	78.2 - 100.0
Problem solving	60.0	50.0 - 60.0	36.17	0			1	6.7%	0.2 - 31.9	14	93.3%	68.1 - 99.8
Personal social	60.0	40.0 - 60.0	35.84	3	20.0%	4.3 - 48.1	2	13.3%	1.7 - 40.5	10	66.7%	38.4 - 88.2
Follow up at 12 months - n = 2												
Communication	60.0	60.0 - 60.0	15.62	0			0			2	100.0%	15.8 - 100.0
Gross motor	60.0	55.0 - 60.0	21.49	0			0			2	100.0%	15.8 - 100.0
Fine motor	57.5	55.0 - 60.0	34.5	0			0			2	100.0%	15.8 - 100.0
Problem solving	57.5	55.0 - 60.0	27.32	0			0			2	100.0%	15.8 - 100.0
Personal social	60.0	60.0 - 60.0	21.73	0			0			2	100.0%	15.8 - 100.0
Follow up at 14 months - n = 9												
Communication	50.0	40.0 - 55.0	17.4	0			2	22.2%	2.8 - 60.0	7	77.8%	40.0 - 97.2

Gross motor	55.0	30.0 - 60.0	25.8	2	22.2%	2.8 - 60.0	1	11.1%	0.3 - 48.2	6	66.7%	29.9 - 92.5
Fine motor	50.0	30.0 - 60.0	23.06	1	11.1%	0.3 - 48.2	2	22.2%	2.8 - 60.0	6	66.7%	29.9 - 92.5
Problem solving	45.0	40.0 - 50.0	22.56	0			2	22.2%	2.8 - 60.0	7	77.8%	40.0 - 97.2
Personal social	45.0	35.0 - 50.0	23.18	2	22.2%	2.8 - 60.0	1	11.1%	0.3 - 48.2	6	66.7%	29.9 - 92.5
Follow up at 24 months - n = 3												
Communication	50.0	50.0 - 55.0	25.17	0			0			3	100.0%	29.2 - 100.0
Gross motor	50.0	45.0 - 60.0	38.07	0			1	33.3%	0.8 - 90.6	2	66.7%	9.4 - 99.2
Fine motor	60.0	55.0 - 60.0	35.16	0			0			3	100.0%	29.2 - 100.0
Problem solving	45.0	45.0 - 55.0	29.78	0			0			3	100.0%	29.2 - 100.0
Personal social	40.0	40.0 - 55.0	31.54	0			2	66.7%	9.4 - 99.2	1	33.3%	0.8 - 90.6

Figure 3: Graphic representing ASQ-3 neurodevelopment categories, by period of assessment and overall.

A total of 10 (33%) of children had at least one subdomain defined as low in their assessment. One of them were born extremely preterm at 26 weeks of gestation for spontaneous placental disruption. The new-born was diagnosed with multiple complications at birth including immediate thrombocytopenia/anaemia, respiratory distress syndrome, sepsis, meningitis, hyperbilirubinemia, postnatal confirmed cytomegalovirus infection, intraventricular haemorrhage grade 3. He stayed 5 months in NICU and was discharged home at 6 months of life. He was admitted to hospital several times in the following months for hydrocephalus and was treated by ventriculo-peritoneal shunt. He was diagnosed with motor development delayed and was closely followed by paediatricians. He had ASQ-3 low scores in gross motor, fine motor and personal social subdomains at 14 months.

Another infant was born extremely preterm at 25 weeks of gestation because of placental disruption without administration of antenatal corticosteroids. The new-born was admitted to NICU for prematurity, respiratory distress syndrome and hyperbilirubinemia and stayed 3 months before he was discharged home. He had an ASQ-3 low score in gross motor at 8 months.

The 8 other children were born at term (37 to 41 weeks of gestations). All parents completed secondary school or more and no major pregnancy condition was reported. New-borns had no complications after birth, but one was tested positive for SARS-CoV-2 at the maternity. Out of 6 patients assessed at 8 months, 3 had a low score in the gross motor subdomain and the 3 others had a low score in the personal social subdomain. Two new-borns were assessed at 14 months including one with a low score in the gross motor subdomain and the other one in the personal social subdomain.

The new-born tested positive for SARS-CoV-2 at the maternity was born at 41 weeks. The mother had a SARS-CoV-2 positive test at 39 weeks and 5 days. She presented mild symptoms with only anosmia and ageusia. The new-born was asymptomatic and the blood cord SARS-CoV-2 PCR was negative at birth. The 8 months ASQ-3 subdomain scores were within the normal range for communication (55; cut-off 29.65), fine motor (60; cut-off 25.14), problem solving (45; cut-off 27.72) and personal social (45; cut-off 25.34). The only subdomain below the cut-off was gross motor (20; cut-off 22.25)

Considering the mother who was admitted in ICU for COVID-19, she gave birth preterm at 32 wk after receiving antenatal corticosteroids. The patient delivered by caesarean section because she required mechanical ventilation. Intravenous clarithromycin and hydroxychloroquine were administered as a COVID-19 related medicine before birth. The new-born stayed 45 days in NICU for prematurity, respiratory distress syndrome and anemia, and was discharged home. The mother was discharged after a total of 34 days at hospital including 2 weeks in ICU. All the 24 months ASQ-3 subdomains' scores were in the normal range; communication (50; cut-off 25.17), gross motor (50; cut-off 38.07), fine motor (60; cut-off 35.16), problem solving (45; cut-off 29.78) and personal social (40; cut-off 31.54).

Ongoing data collection

Out of the 8 initial centres willing to participate to the study, only 2 collected data (Lausanne, Switzerland and Los Angeles, USA) and one had finalized ethical committee approval process (Dublin, Ireland). The 5 remaining sites were not able to take part to the study due to lack of resources during the pandemic context.

As of July, 2022, 6 additional COVI-PREG sites have shown their interest and have taken the necessary steps to participate in the follow-up of the infant data: Araau (Switzerland), Bern (Switzerland), Chur (Switzerland), Basel (Switzerland), Sao Paulo (Brazil) and Riyadh (Saudi Arabia). Therefore, data collection will continue following the submission of this report.

11. DISCUSSION

Key results

Our study reported no major signs of significant global neurodevelopment delay in infant born from mother tested positive to SARS-CoV-2 during pregnancy. At the time of this report the cohort is limited by its size and therefore no stratified analysis could be performed regarding COVID-19 related medicine use as only one patient was administered clarithromycin with hydroxychloroquine before birth.

As the cohort grows, attention will be paid to the gross motor and personal and social scores of the children as in this first group analysis, higher rates of below average ratings were obtained. However, the 6-8 and 12-14 months' time points assessments reported few cases of low scores defined as below the official cut-off, which means that the infant is potentially delayed in one domain of his/her development and should be evaluated by a professional, according to the ASQ-3 assessments tool recommendations. Scores were below the cut-off for gross motor (4/16 at 6-8 months and 2/11 at 12-14 months), fine motor (1/11 at 12-14 months) and personal social (3/16 at 6-8 months and 2/11 at 12-14 months) assessment.

A study by Shuffrey et al. highlighted significant lower scores in infants born during the pandemic (exposed and unexposed patients) than a historical cohort before the COVID-19 outbreak, on gross motor, fine motor and personal social fields at a 6 months follow up assessment.²⁴ However, no differences were found in ASQ-3 subdomains mean scores between exposed and unexposed to SARS-CoV-2 patients during the pandemic period. They described the number of cases below the cut-offs in exposed and unexposed patients with 26 (22.8%) vs 27 (19.1%) infants with at least one subdomain below the cut-off, respectively. They did not test for statistical differences and this information was missing for the pre-pandemic historical cohort. The similar ASQ-3 scores of children born from exposed and unexposed pregnant women could be also explained by the prenatal stress caused by the pandemic itself regardless of the viral exposure, which can affect the fetal development

through complex and still not clear mechanisms.²⁵ Another recent article by Edlow et al. reported that pregnant women exposed to SARS-CoV-2 during pregnancy were associated with an increased risk of offspring language disorder at 1 year of life compared to non-exposed patients, based on diagnosis codes of a cohort of more than 7000 patients.²⁶ However, given the age of these young children the precision of such a diagnosis is likely to be limited.

The initial hypothesis of a possible delayed neurodevelopment of children exposed to SARS-CoV-2 was based on other viral exposures evidence such as HIV and Zika. Although our cohort size is small at this first reporting point, the severity of the impact of Zika virus was detectable at this developmental time point and with similar sized populations.¹⁵ Therefore we are able to rule out a substantial impact of SARS-CoV-2 on the development of the human nervous system to a similar level seen in Zika Virus. Children exposed to HIV (mother positive to HIV) during pregnancy but not infected at birth reported an increased motor delay in childhood, compared to unexposed children.¹⁶ Similarly a study reported that the 1918 influenza A/H1N1 pandemic was associated with a lower child educational level attainment.²⁷ The basis of this hypothesis comes from studies reporting that maternal immune modification could impact the fetal brain development,²⁸ and recent studies have shown that SARS-CoV-2 infection was associated with increased cytokine levels in pregnant women, marker of the immune response, and was correlated with disease severity.²⁹

Regarding the social and personal development, a hypothesis was raised during the pandemic, related to the context of an environment where people have to wear facial masks, and restricted social contact for periods of time and that social development may be impeded for young children growing up in this period. However, Schneider et al. demonstrated that facial mask did not affect emotion recognition in infants. A total of 276 children aged 3 to 6 years were asked if they can recognize emotions in a set of 90 pictures showing adult actors displaying joy, anger or sadness, with and without facial mask. No difference was reported in the emotions' recognition between masked and non-masked actors.³⁰ It is then unlikely that facial masks is a main factor that could interfere with social personal children but the potential impact of restriction on social interactions remains to be seen.

In our study, no low score was reported at the 24-27 months' time points (0/3) which seems to be reassuring, but extremely limited by the very small number of patients assessed at that time point. Some children may catch up their neurodevelopment delay spontaneously or due to family involvement, medical follow up and potential medical intervention. Early intervention for delayed neurodevelopment children have shown promising results in high risk children and thus reinforce the need to study the impact of SARS-CoV-2 during pregnancy on long term development. The identification of SARS-CoV-2 as a risk factor of neurodevelopment impairment would lead to early and specific interventions to prevent or manage as soon as possible these potential disorders.

Limitations

The main limitation of this study is the very small sample of patients. However, this cohort is continuing to grow and new centres are opening up to the COVI-PREG longer term follow up study. Future reports will be provided on this cohort as the size increases. To date, no study has assessed the impact of COVID-19 related medicine use during pregnancy on the neurodevelopment of infants. Another limitation is related to the selection bias of this type of survey: mothers who delivered prematurely and/or had adverse pregnancy outcomes, severe COVID-19 are more likely to be willing to participate in studies assessing their child's neurodevelopment. Only one patient was exposed to COVID-19 related medicines during pregnancy. Due to scarce safety profiles of medicines used to treat COVID-19 in pregnancy mostly used as repurposing drugs, further study should focus on this concern.

Interpretation

A number of challenges were faced, some were directly attributable to the pandemic and others were more common research administrative delays. Of the eight sites who opted to report on the participants from their centre only two successfully obtained ethical approvals and implemented the protocol before the study end. There were delays and challenges in aspects of obtaining the questionnaire approvals and in other study administrative aspects, however the largest barrier was staff time within the different waves of the COVID-19 pandemic to undertake the required set up duties. However, the number of COVI-PREG sites enrolled in the longer term follow up is increasing now that the most difficult phase of the pandemic has passed and we anticipate larger numbers in the coming 6 months. Our experience highlights the challenges of setting up such international collaborations within the context of an international pandemic and a recommendation is made here that processes and procedures should be established in advance and then implemented when required.

In that context of global pandemic, children are not spared of post-natal SARS-CoV-2 infection. This raises the questions of the difficulty to collect such exposure and potential immune activation as infants present mostly asymptomatic form of COVID-19 in the first years of life, and this could play a role in the neurodevelopment of children.^{31,32}

No conclusions can be drawn from this study at this time point regarding the potential impact of medications used to treat SARS-CoV-2 in pregnancy. However, future reports will follow on a larger sample size. Multiple mechanisms are potentially involved in the neurodevelopment such as disease severity, COVID-19 related drug exposure, prenatal stress, COVID-19 vaccination, post-natal SARS-CoV-2 exposure and this need to be taken in consideration for future studies.

12. CONCLUSION

This study did not report any signals of substantial neurodevelopmental delay in the children born from mothers tested positive to SARS-CoV-2 during pregnancy, but no firm conclusions can be drawn at present regarding more moderate levels of delay as the number of cases included was too small. Current literature is controversial regarding the association of neurodevelopmental impairment in children exposed to SARS-CoV-2 during pregnancy compared to non-exposed. However, the COVID-19 pandemic period seems to be associated with lower neurodevelopment scores compared to the pre-pandemic period. No study to date has assessed the impact of COVID-19 related drugs on children neurodevelopment. All these concerns emphasise the need to perform further studies, as early intervention in high-risk children is beneficial.

13. DISCLAIMER

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